

THE CONTENT OF FORMATION OF CREATIVE ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS IN ADOLESCENT GIRLS

¹Mirsolieva Muhabbat Tukhtasinovna, ²Nigora Tulyaganova Rahmonali kizi

¹Doctor of pedagogical sciences, associate professor

²Doctoral student of the Scientific Research Institute "Family and Women"

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8200445>

Abstract. *In recent years, increasing the socio-political and legal activity of women in Uzbekistan, creating conditions for them to realize their abilities and opportunities in various fields and sectors, and guaranteeing unconditional observance of their rights and legal interests wide-scale work related to provision, strengthening and support of the family institution is being carried out, and the regulatory legal framework is being further improved.*

Keywords: *regulatory legal framework, family institution, legal activity of women.*

In recent years, increasing the socio-political and legal activity of women in Uzbekistan, creating conditions for them to realize their abilities and opportunities in various fields and sectors, and guaranteeing unconditional observance of their rights and legal interests wide-scale work related to provision, strengthening and support of the family institution is being carried out, and the regulatory legal framework is being further improved.

It is known that entrepreneurial activity is an initiative activity aimed at obtaining income (profit) carried out by the subjects of entrepreneurial activity in accordance with the law, taking risks and under their own property responsibility.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Freedom of Entrepreneurial Activity" defines the concept of entrepreneurial activity as follows: "Entrepreneurial activity (entrepreneurial activity) is carried out by the subjects of entrepreneurial activity in accordance with the law, taking risks and owning their own property. proactive activity aimed at obtaining income (profit) under his responsibility".

The essence of entrepreneurship is further clarified through the following.

First of all, who can be the subject of entrepreneurship? According to the law, every citizen who has reached the age of majority can engage in any type of activity that does not contradict the law based on his own property or on the basis of the authority of the owner of the property.

Secondly, in the above definition, another aspect of entrepreneurship is expressed - its content, which is rich in content and has a diverse appearance. Choosing, organizing and developing entrepreneurial activity is essentially not a matter of state and social importance, but a freely chosen activity.

Creative entrepreneurship is a widely and rapidly developing form of entrepreneurship.

Creativity (creatio) is a departure from standard, traditional rules and templates, and the ability of a person to be creative and creative is counted.

American psychologist Dj.Gilford divides personality thinking into divergent and convergent thinking. In this case, divergent thinking reflects creativity that involves making decisions in different approaches to a specific situation, while convergent thinking is defined by the characteristic of offering the same approach and repeated solutions in different situations. In turn, the researcher expresses divergent thinking as a way of thinking that develops the creative abilities of a person. In our opinion, creativity is a non-standard way of thinking of a person, in

which a person's thinking, scope of imagination, risk-taking qualities, fantasy and worldview are important.

During our scientific-pedagogical analysis, we paid attention to the theoretical study of the problem of formation of creative entrepreneurial skills in girls.

Researcher M.Artikova, based on the cooperation of her general school and family, in her research work aimed at developing entrepreneurial skills in students, the formation of social perceptions, values and the formation of value systems as factors affecting the development of entrepreneurial skills in students. , emphasizes that the educational process in family cooperation, their self-management, participation in research activities, and creativity are important.

Pedagogical scientist O.Musurmonova, before analyzing the motivating factors for the entrepreneurial activity of modern women, dwells on some of its characteristics and substantiates the following:

First of all, the importance of mental capacity in entrepreneurial activity is incomparable. In addition, qualities such as knowledge, the ability to anticipate difficulties, the ability to find solutions to social problems, the ability to foresee the causes and consequences of the work to be done, and the ability to take a creative approach make it possible to determine the goals and objectives of an entrepreneur and to plan his activities rationally. .

secondly, an entrepreneur should have the ability to communicate with people. For example, drawing correct conclusions from the opinion of the majority, patiently listening to the opinions of others, being able to defend one's point of view and interests until the end in necessary cases, and being able to explain one's opinion to people of different genders and ages are among such qualities.

thirdly, since an entrepreneur is often forced to take risks, he must have a strong will. And for this, courage, effort, the ability to control one's desires and needs, competitiveness, striving for a goal, gaining the attention of many by demonstrating the qualities characteristic of one's "me", determination , qualities such as demandingness, courage, and boldness are required.

fourthly, an entrepreneur must have a healthy body, a healthy mind, and a healthy mind as he takes on a lot of responsibility and works tirelessly day and night.

The analysis of foreign experiences shows that the "Female Entrepreneurship Global Index" (Female Entrepreneurship Index - FEI) measures the development prospects of women's entrepreneurship all over the world. In this gender index, the quality of the development of women's entrepreneurship is determined by the following 3 main factors:

- entrepreneurial environment (Entrepreneurial Environment);
- entrepreneurial ecosystem (Entrepreneurial Eco-System);
- Entrepreneurial Aspirations of women.

From the above analysis, when it comes to entrepreneurship, especially creative entrepreneurship, first of all, special attention should be paid to the formation of qualities related to creativity, risk-taking, and initiative in the individual, as well as the desire of students to engage in entrepreneurship in this process. it can be concluded that it is necessary to create an educational and educational environment aimed at support and development.

Based on our empirical observations, it is appropriate to single out the following as important aspects of the development of creative entrepreneurial qualities in schoolchildren:

- the involvement of schoolchildren in business activities plays an important role in improving the level of well-being of families;

- as a result of the entrepreneurship of schoolgirls, positive socially significant norms are formed in their behavior in relation to men;

- business technologies implemented by schoolgirls on the basis of creative entrepreneurship are considered significant due to their rapid adaptation to modern changes, richness in innovations and social orientation.

In fact, women's entrepreneurship differs from men's entrepreneurship in terms of its motives and social orientation, which makes it necessary to take into account the gender specificity of women's entrepreneurship.

The dictionary meaning of the concept of "gender" means the Latin "genus", that is, "sex". If biological sex divides people into women and men, then gender is aimed at separating the place of women and men in society. In order for women and men to find and determine their place in society, the state creates the same conditions and opportunities for them, which serves as the basis for ensuring gender equality.

Gender is a social aspect of the relationship between women and men that is manifested in all spheres of society's life and activities, including politics, economy, law, ideology and culture, education and science.

It is known that a person is not born with concepts about gender, they are acquired from childhood in the family, school, workplace and society. For example, in most families, similar ideas about suitable and superior professions for girls and boys direct boys to engineering, law and medicine, and business. The gender imbalance in the choice of fields is manifested in the participation of girls in household work or agricultural work, in their activity in the household sector. The same is true in the field of entrepreneurship. The first obstacle that most women who want to do business face is lack of confidence in them, lack of family support and lack of social connections. Such gender stereotypes prevent women from realizing their potential.

Gender relations reflect the changes taking place in the life of society.

After the independence of Uzbekistan, fundamental changes were made in the life of the state and society, and all-round national development was made possible.

One of the important components of the renewal process is a constructive gender policy. From the first days of independent national development, the issue of increasing the role of women in the family and society was defined as one of the priorities of state policy. At the same time, the issue of developing women's entrepreneurial skills was also noted as one of the priority strategies of our state policy.

Therefore, in the development of work in this field, in the development of the skills of female students in entrepreneurship, in particular, in creative entrepreneurship, the organization of career guidance for girls in cooperation between family, neighborhood and school, in which they are not based on socio-cultural restrictions, but explaining how to make a choice suitable for their abilities, as well as developing girls' knowledge in the field of creative entrepreneurship, ICT, STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics); it is expedient to organize special educational courses and start-up contests that serve to increase the socio-economic, political and legal activity of girls in the neighborhood.

REFERENCES

1. Hamroyev H. Tadbirkorlik asoslari. - T.: Yangi nashr, 2010. - 360 b.
2. Корецкая Г. Модель Дорожной Карты развития креативной экономики в странах

Центральной Азии. - 41 с.

3. Тадбиркорлик ва бизнес асослари: Касб-хунар коллежлари ва академик лицейлар учун ўқув қўлланма. 6-нашр./ З.Худойбердиевнинг умумий таҳрири остида; -Т.: “ИЛМ ЗИЁ”, 2014 - 342 б.
4. Z. Mahkamova, O. Musurmanova, R. Turdiboeva “Oqila ayollar-farovon oila tayanchi” uslubiy qo’llanma Toshkent 2023 yil
5. M.Ortiqova “Umumta’lim maktabi va oila hamkorligi asosida o’quvchilarda tadbirkorlik k’nikmalarini rivojlantirish” p.f.d. dissertatsiyasi Andijon 2020 yil
6. <https://huquqiyportal.uz/dictionary>